

Investigation Gas Sensing Performance of Yttrium Oxide Thick film Sensors

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Abstract:

The present research focuses on developing thick film gas sensors of Y₂O₃ nanoparticles and evaluating their gas sensing performance. The thick film sensors were fabricated on a glass substrate using a cost-effective screen-printing technique and tested against hazardous gases such as NO₂, H₂S, LPG, NH₃ and C₂H₆O using a static gas sensing system. The results revealed that the Y₂O₃ thick film sensors exhibited the highest sensitivity of 73.15% towards NO₂ gas at an optimal operating temperature of 200°C and a gas concentration of 1000 ppm. The sensors demonstrated excellent selectivity and reproducibility towards NO₂, with response and recovery times of 15 and 96 seconds, respectively. The developed thick films were characterized by FESEM, EDX and XRD to study the morphology, element analysis and crystallographic structure respectively. These findings highlight the potential of Y₂O₃-based thick film sensors for efficient NO₂ detection in environmental and industrial monitoring applications.

Keywords: Rare earth metal oxides, bandgap, gas sensors, reproducibility, environmental.

1. Introduction

Gas sensors have witnessed significant advancements in recent years due to the growing demand for efficient, sensitive, and selective gas detection in various fields, including environmental monitoring, industrial safety, healthcare, and automotive applications [1, 2]. Traditional gas sensors, such as metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) sensors, have been enhanced through nanostructuring, surface modification, and hybrid material integration, leading to improved sensitivity, faster response time, and lower detection limits [2, 3]. Innovations in binary metal oxides, perovskites, and 2D materials like graphene derivatives have further expanded the possibilities for highly selective and stable

gas sensors [4, 5]. With the rise in pollution levels, workplace hazards, and the need for real-time gas detection in smart technologies, the development of advanced gas sensors is crucial for ensuring safety, health, and environmental sustainability [5-7].

Rare earth metal oxides (REOs) are a class of materials derived from rare earth elements (lanthanides, scandium, and yttrium) that exhibit unique chemical, optical, electronic, and catalytic properties [8, 9]. These oxides, such as Yttrium oxide (Y_2O_3), cerium oxide (CeO_2), lanthanum oxide (La_2O_3), and neodymium oxide (Nd_2O_3), have found extensive applications in catalysis, gas sensing, fuel cells, optical coatings, and electronic devices. Their high oxygen storage capacity, excellent thermal stability, and redox behavior make them ideal for use in catalytic converters, solid oxide fuel cells, and photocatalytic systems [9]. REOs play a crucial role in improving the performance of semiconductors and luminescent materials. Ongoing research focuses on nanostructuring, doping, and composite formation to enhance their functional properties for emerging technologies, such as energy storage, environmental remediation, and advanced sensors [9, 10]. REOs have emerged as promising materials for gas sensing applications due to their unique electronic configurations, high oxygen vacancy concentrations, and excellent thermal stability. Recent advancements focus on enhancing their sensitivity, selectivity, and response time through nanostructuring, doping, and composite formation [10, 11].

Yttrium oxide (Y_2O_3) nanoparticles are widely studied rare earth metal oxides due to their unique properties. It has gained significant attention in gas sensing applications due to its wide bandgap, high oxygen ion conductivity, and excellent thermal and chemical stability [11, 12]. These nanoparticles typically exhibit a cubic crystal structure, a high melting point ($\sim 2430^\circ C$), and strong luminescent properties, making them ideal for applications in phosphors, laser materials, and bioimaging [12]. Y_2O_3 nanoparticles can be synthesized using various methods, including sol-gel, co-precipitation, hydrothermal, and combustion techniques, each influencing particle size, morphology, and crystallinity. Due to their excellent optical transparency and high refractive index, they are widely used in coatings, ceramics, and display technologies [13, 14]. The doped Y_2O_3 nanoparticles, particularly with europium (Eu^{3+}), are extensively utilized in red phosphors for LEDs and plasma display panels. In biomedical applications, their biocompatibility and fluorescence properties make them suitable for drug delivery and bioimaging [15, 16]. Furthermore, their superior

chemical and thermal resistance enables their use in catalyst supports, gas sensors, and high-temperature structural materials [16, 17].

The present work focuses on investigating the gas sensing performance of yttrium oxide (Y_2O_3) thick film sensors through structural characterizations using Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM), Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX), and X-ray Diffraction (XRD). By correlating these structural characterizations with sensor performance metrics such as sensitivity, selectivity, response and recovery time.

2. Experimental work:

The fig. 1 illustrates the step-by-step process for developing Y_2O_3 thick film sensors using the screen-printing technique.

Fig. 1. Steps of development of Y_2O_3 thick film sensor using screen printing technique

The commercially available AR-grade Y_2O_3 nanoparticles are used to prepare a thixotropic paste. This paste is formulated with a proper combination of inorganic (70%) and organic (30%) chemicals to ensure the desired viscosity and printability [18, 19]. The screen-printing setup, consisting of a nylon screen with a 120-mesh size, is utilized to deposit the paste onto glass substrates, which are positioned appropriately beneath the mesh. The

prepared paste is then transferred onto the substrates using a squeegee to uniform deposition. The printed films are subsequently dried under an infrared (IR) lamp for 30 minutes to remove solvents and stabilize the film structure [19, 20]. Finally, the Y_2O_3 thick films are annealed in a closed muffle furnace at 200°C for 3 hours to enhance their structural and sensing properties.

3. Result and discussion:

Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) is an advanced imaging technique used to obtain high-resolution surface morphology of materials at the nanometer scale. Unlike conventional Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), which utilizes a thermionic emission source. The FESEM micrograph of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor is reveal in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. FESEM micrograph of Y_2O_3 thick film sensor

The FESEM micrograph provides a detailed visualization of its surface morphology and particle distribution. The image, captured at a magnification of 100,000×, reveals the presence of agglomerated nanoparticles with a highly porous structure, which is beneficial for gas sensing applications due to enhanced surface area and gas adsorption sites [21, 22]. The measured particle sizes range from approximately 13.49 nm to 32.38 nm, indicating nanoscale features that contribute to improved sensitivity and response time. The FESEM micrograph also shows a non-uniform, rough surface morphology, which can facilitate better gas interaction [9, 10]. The high-resolution imaging confirms the nanostructured

nature of the Y_2O_3 thick film, which is crucial for optimizing its performance in gas sensing applications by ensuring better gas diffusion and adsorption on the sensor surface. The specific surface area (S_w) was measured using eq. 1 [20], and it was recorded as $3.62 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$.

$$S_w = 6/\rho d \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where,

S_w is the specific surface area, 6 is a constant, d is the diameter of the spherical particle, and ρ is the density of Y_2O_3 .

The EDX spectrum of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor shown in Fig. 3, confirms the elemental composition of the developed films.

Fig. 3. EDX spectrum of Y_2O_3 thick film sensor

The EDX spectrum displays prominent peaks corresponding to yttrium (Y) and oxygen (O), verifying the successful formation of Y_2O_3 without any detectable impurities. The elemental analysis table shows that yttrium constitutes 79.00% by weight (40.36% atomic percentage), while oxygen accounts for 21.00% by weight (59.64% atomic percentage), aligning well with the expected stoichiometry of Y_2O_3 . The absence of unwanted elements in the spectrum indicates the high purity of the developed thick films, which is essential for ensuring reliable and reproducible gas sensing performance [18, 19].

This characterization supports the structural and compositional integrity of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor, making it a suitable candidate for gas sensing applications.

Fig. 4. EDX mapping of Y_2O_3 thick film sensor

The EDX elemental mapping of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor display in Fig. 4, provides a spatial distribution of yttrium (Y) and oxygen (O) across the film surface. The mapping reveals a uniform dispersion of both elements, indicating the homogeneous composition of the Y_2O_3 thick film. Yttrium is highlighted in yellow, while oxygen is marked in green, confirming their consistent presence throughout the material. The well-distributed elemental composition ensures good phase purity and uniformity, which are essential for stable and efficient gas sensing performance. The porous and agglomerated structure observed in the mapping further supports enhanced gas adsorption, which can improve sensor sensitivity and response time. This characterization reinforces the suitability of Y_2O_3 thick films for gas sensing applications by verifying their structural integrity and compositional consistency.

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor reveal in Fig. 5, confirms its crystalline nature and phase purity. The observed diffraction peaks correspond to the cubic phase of yttrium oxide (Y_2O_3), matching the standard JCPDS card No. 41-1105 [23, 24]. The prominent diffraction peaks are indexed to the (211), (222), (400), (411), (332), (431), (440), (611), (631), and (622) crystallographic planes. The most intense peak at $2\theta \approx$

29.21° corresponds to the (222) plane, which is characteristic of the cubic phase of Y_2O_3 [24, 25].

Fig. 5. XRD pattern of Y_2O_3 thick film sensor

The sharp and well-defined diffraction peaks indicate good crystallinity, while the absence of additional peaks confirms the phase purity of the developed Y_2O_3 thick film. The crystallite size was estimated using the Debye Scherrer equation eq. 2 [25], and it was found to be 55.86 nm.

$$\text{Crystallite size} = K\lambda / (\beta \cos\theta) \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Where,

D-Crystallite size, K-Constant (0.94), λ - wavelength, β -full-width at half maxima (0.1532), and θ -angle of diffraction.

In gas sensing applications, key performance parameters include sensitivity, selectivity, limit of detection (LOD), and response and recovery times. Sensitivity refers to the sensor's ability to detect and quantify gas concentration changes, typically expressed as the ratio of resistance or conductance change upon exposure to the target gas. Higher sensitivity ensures better detection of low gas concentrations [19, 26]. Selectivity is the sensor's capability to distinguish a specific gas from other interfering gases in the environment, which is crucial for practical applications. Limit of Detection (LOD) represents

the lowest gas concentration that the sensor can reliably detect, often determined by signal-to-noise ratio considerations. A lower LOD indicates a more precise and efficient sensor. Response time is the duration required for the sensor to reach a stable signal after gas exposure, while recovery time is the time needed for the sensor to return to its baseline state after the gas is removed. In the gas sensing study the sensitivity, selectivity, limit of detection and response and recovery time parameters were investigated by using static gas sensing system [20]. The sensitivity versus operating temperature plot is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Sensitivity versus operating temperature plot of Y₂O₃ thick film sensor

Fig. 6. illustrates the gas sensing performance of the Y₂O₃ thick film sensor for different gases, including NO₂, H₂S, LPG, NH₃, and ethanol. Sensitivity is plotted as a function of temperature, ranging from 50°C to 250°C, revealing the sensor's optimal operating temperature. From the graph, it is evident that the sensitivity of the sensor increases with temperature, reaching a peak at 200°C, and then decreases at 250°C. Among the tested gases, the highest sensitivity is observed for NO₂, followed by H₂S, LPG, NH₃, and ethanol in descending order. This trend indicates that Y₂O₃ has a strong affinity for NO₂ molecules, likely due to its strong adsorption and charge transfer interactions with oxygen species on the sensor surface [20, 21]. The decrease in sensitivity beyond 200°C suggests desorption of gas molecules at higher temperatures, reducing the sensor's response. The variations in response for different gases can be attributed to differences in adsorption energy, reaction

kinetics, and charge carrier interactions with the Y_2O_3 surface. These results confirm that the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor exhibits the highest sensitivity to NO_2 at an optimal temperature of $200^\circ C$, making it a promising candidate for selective NO_2 detection [20, 22].

The selectivity histogram the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor is shown in Fig. 7, illustrates the response of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor to different gases, highlighting its preferential detection capability. The bar chart shows the selectivity of NO_2 , H_2S , LPG, NH_3 , and C_2H_6O gases, with NO_2 exhibiting the highest selectivity. The NO_2 gas has the highest response, indicating that Y_2O_3 has a strong interaction with NO_2 molecules, likely due to its strong electron-withdrawing nature, which enhances charge transfer interactions on the sensor surface. H_2S and LPG also show moderate responses, while NH_3 and ethanol exhibit the lowest selectivity, suggesting weaker adsorption and reaction kinetics with the Y_2O_3 surface [22, 23]. This selectivity trend confirms that Y_2O_3 is highly selective toward NO_2 , making it a potential candidate for NO_2 gas sensing applications.

Fig. 7. Selectivity histogram of Y_2O_3 thick film sensor

The sensitivity vs. NO_2 gas concentration plot is illustrate Fig. 8, illustrates the response of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor to varying concentrations of NO_2 gas. The graph demonstrates a positive correlation between sensitivity and NO_2 concentration, indicating an increase in sensitivity as the NO_2 concentration rises from 200 ppm to 1000 ppm. At lower concentrations ~ 200 ppm, the sensor exhibits a moderate response, which increases significantly with increasing NO_2 levels, reaching above 73.15% sensitivity at 1000 ppm. This

behavior suggests that Y_2O_3 has a high affinity for NO_2 molecules, likely due to strong adsorption and charge transfer interactions. The observed trend can be attributed to the modulation of charge carrier concentration in the sensing material upon NO_2 exposure. As an electron-withdrawing gas, NO_2 acts as an acceptor, capturing free electrons from the conduction band of Y_2O_3 , leading to increased resistance and enhanced sensitivity. The nonlinear nature of the plot suggests that saturation may occur at higher concentrations [23].

Fig. 8. Sensitivity versus NO_2 gas concentration plot of Y_2O_3 thick film sensor

Fig. 9. Response and recovery time plot of Y_2O_3 thick film sensor to NO_2 gas

The response and recovery time plot is display Fig. 9, illustrates the dynamic behavior of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor upon exposure to NO_2 gas. The graph shows the variation in resistance over time, demonstrating both the response time (ON Time) and recovery time (OFF Time) of the sensor. When NO_2 gas is introduced at ≈ 15 seconds, the resistance of the Y_2O_3 sensor decreases significantly. The resistance reaches a minimum at ≈ 75 seconds, indicating that the adsorption of NO_2 molecules has reached equilibrium, stabilizing the electrical properties of the sensor. At ≈ 94 seconds, NO_2 gas is removed, and the resistance begins to recover. The resistance increases as the adsorbed NO_2 molecules desorb from the surface, restoring the sensor to its initial state [26, 27]. The observed response and recovery behavior confirm the fast response and good reversibility of the Y_2O_3 sensor, making it suitable for real-time NO_2 gas detection applications [20, 25]. The rapid desorption suggests that the sensor material has weakly bonded gas molecules, facilitating quick recovery and reuse [27, 28].

Conclusions

The thick film sensors were developed on a glass substrate using a cost-effective screen-printing technique. The structural and morphological characteristics of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor were analyzed using FESEM, EDX, and XRD techniques. FESEM analysis revealed

a highly porous and uniformly distributed grain structure, which is beneficial for enhanced gas adsorption and desorption processes, thereby improving the sensor's sensitivity. The EDX spectrum confirmed the elemental composition, showing strong peaks for yttrium (Y) and oxygen (O), verifying the purity of the synthesized Y_2O_3 material. The XRD pattern exhibited sharp and well-defined peaks corresponding to the cubic Y_2O_3 phase, in agreement with standard JCPDS data, confirming the crystallinity of the material.

The gas sensing performance of the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor was systematically evaluated through sensitivity, selectivity, concentration-dependent response, and dynamic response characteristics. The sensitivity vs. temperature plot demonstrated that the sensor exhibited maximum sensitivity towards NO_2 gas at $200^\circ C$, confirming its optimal operating temperature. The selectivity histogram revealed that the sensor had the highest selectivity towards NO_2 compared to H_2S , LPG, NH_3 , and C_2H_6O , indicating its strong affinity for NO_2 molecules. The sensitivity vs. NO_2 gas concentration plot showed a direct correlation between gas concentration and sensor response, with a steady increase in sensitivity up to 1000 ppm, highlighting its potential for detecting varying levels of NO_2 . The response and recovery time analysis demonstrated a rapid response upon NO_2 exposure, followed by a fast recovery, indicating good repeatability and stability. These findings suggest that the Y_2O_3 thick film sensor is a promising candidate for highly selective and sensitive NO_2 detection, making it suitable for environmental monitoring and industrial applications.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

We declare that, we have not received any funding for the research work and we have no conflict of interest for our research work.

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